

DEVELOPMENT OF A NOVEL EDGE DETECTION METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Accurate edge detection is fundamental to various image processing tasks. This paper presents a novel edge detection method that goes beyond traditional approaches. We propose a multichannel edge detection method that can be superior to the single-channel edge detection method.

Introduction

Edge detection is a fundamental technique in image processing [1-2] that plays a crucial role in tasks such as object recognition, image segmentation, and content analysis [3-4]. Traditional methods for edge detection rely on filtering techniques that can identify abrupt changes in intensity between pixels [5]. However, these methods can sometimes be affected by issues such as sensitivity to noise, blurring of edges, and difficulty in capturing intricate details. In recent years, various researchers have conducted research on the development of edge detection methods [6-9].

The proposed method

Figure 1. Novel edge detection method

The given method in Figure 1 works with following mathematical expressions:

$$Rx = R * Sx = \sum_{k=0}^{rows} \sum_{l=0}^{cols} Rx_{k,l} = \sum_{i=0}^3 \sum_{j=0}^3 R_{k+i,k+j} Sx_{i,j} \quad (1)$$

$$Ry = R * Sy = \sum_{k=0}^{rows} \sum_{l=0}^{cols} Ry_{k,l} = \sum_{i=0}^3 \sum_{j=0}^3 R_{k+i,k+j} Sy_{i,j} \quad (2)$$

$$Re = \sum_{k=0}^{rows} \sum_{l=0}^{cols} Re_{k,l} = Rx_{k,l} | Ry_{k,l} \quad (3)$$

$$edge = Re \& Ge \mid Re \& Be \mid Ge \& Be \quad (4)$$

Here: Sx, Sy – Sobel filters in matrix form, R- red channel pixel values in matrix form, Rx, Ry – Sx and Sy filtered matrixes, Re, Ge, Be – edges by R, G, B channels.

Results

Figure 2. The proposed multichannel edge detection method

According to the figure (see Figure 2) shown above each letter means the following: a) input image; b) Edge obtained using R channel; c) Edge obtained using G channel; d) Edge obtained using B channel; e) Final result

Figure 3. Edge obtained using single-channel edge detection method

Single channel

Multi channel (ours)

Figure 4. Comparison of the obtained results on single-channel edge detection and the proposed method

It can be seen from Figure 4 that the proposed method detects edges that are missed by the single-channel approach.

Conclusion

In this paper, a novel edge detection method is developed. Our method outperforms an existing single-channel edge detection method. In future work, we will focus on the following: the use of other popular image datasets; getting better results; and applying the proposed method in various fields.

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